

1 **Reduced repetition of Common Chaffinch's social calls near scree**
2 **slopes in a Mediterranean forest.**

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16

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 Birds use songs and calls as communicative signals. The production of bird
29 vocalizations depends on stimuli that prompt or deter communications. The quartzite
30 scree slopes (*pedrizas*) in the Mediterranean forests of southwestern Spain might
31 potentially engender conflict situation for bird communication. These open areas entail
32 enhanced sound transmission and heightened predation. In this study, we investigate
33 whether the presence of *pedrizas* influences the characteristics of Common Chaffinch
34 (*Fringilla coelebs*) social calls. We employed portable recorders to capture Chaffinch
35 vocalizations both within the forest and in the proximity to the *pedrizas* in the
36 Mediterranean forest of the Monfragüe National Park (Spain). We found that the
37 number of ‘chink’ repeats in Chaffinch social calls was reduced in proximity to *pedrizas*
38 compared to those recorded in the forest. This trend persisted across different
39 conditions. Our finding lends support to the coexistence of stimuli in *pedrizas* that both
40 prompt and deter bird communication. As a consequence, a conflict might arise, leading
41 Chaffinches to potentially respond by emitting social calls while simultaneously
42 shortening the duration of vocalizations to minimize the risk of attracting undetected
43 predators.

44

45 **Keywords:** bird communication, *Fringilla coelebs*, recording, sound transmission,
46 trade-off

47

48 **Introduction**

49 Birds utilize vocalizations (songs and calls) as communicative signals to convey
50 information (Catchpole and Slater 2008). Songs and calls differ in complexity, duration,
51 and the context of vocalization. Songs typically exhibit greater complexity and duration
52 compared to calls. Songs are commonly linked to territorial defence, courtship, and
53 mating behaviours, whereas calls are normally associated with alarm signals and social
54 cohesion within bird population (Catchpole and Slater 2008, but see Rose et al. 2021).

55 The Common Chaffinch (*Fringilla coelebs*) is a widely distributed passerine bird
56 (Cramp et al. 1994, Glutz von Blotzheim and Bauer 1997) frequently utilized as a
57 subject for bioacoustic studies (Marler 1956; Slater et al. 1980; Leitao et al. 2004;
58 Riebel et al. 2015; Cooper et al. 2023). This species inhabits various habitats, including
59 gardens and woodlands (Macleod et al. 2004), and exhibits diverse vocalizations, each
60 proposed to serve particular functions (Marler 1956). For instance, Marler (2004)
61 proposed that the vocal repertory of the Chaffinch comprises the song and eight basic
62 calls: separation/alarm, flight, aggression, courtship, alarm/rain, alarm/hawk,
63 courtship/“kseep”, and courtship/“tchirp” calls. In this study, we investigate the
64 separation/alarm call proposed in Marler (2004). This call consists of a “chink”
65 vocalization that can be emitted as a single note or can be sequentially repeated for a
66 variable number of times. The chink call can be produced by both males and females
67 throughout the year (Marler 2004). The acoustic characteristic of the chinks and the
68 number of repetitions can be regarded as different call types, each potentially serving

69 specific functions (Cramp et al. 1994, Marler 2004). For instance, single chinks emitted
70 at a low rate (5-10 per min) are considered to be contact calls, whereas chinks grouped
71 in groups of two to eight elements, with 70-75 notes per minute, can be classified as
72 mobbing calls (used to encourage other individuals to join a flock mobbing a predator;
73 Marler 1956; Saur et al. 1996; Glutz von Blotzheim and Bauer 1997; Randler and
74 Förschler 2011). Territorial disputes have been suggested as a motivation for emitting
75 chink calls (Marler 1956; Budka et al. 2019). Therefore, variations in the acoustic
76 properties of the chink call may occur due to different motivational variables and may
77 serve specific functions.

78 Conversely, acoustic variations in vocalizations can be equivalent and might be used
79 interchangeably by birds, rather than being restricted to specific context with specific
80 functions (Riebel and Slater 1999). Accordingly, Chaffinches can alternatively emit
81 single or repeated chink calls without a discernible change, at least in external stimuli.
82 Furthermore, bird calls such as the Chaffinch's chink exhibit considerable variation,
83 suggesting it might act as a multi-function signal (Marler 2004). The existence of
84 geographical learned dialects and the challenge in assigning functions to certain
85 Chaffinch calls hinder the establishment of clear relationships between calls and
86 specific functions (Batista 1990; Marler 2004; Luther and Baptista 2010; de Framond et
87 al. 2024). However, the Chaffinch chink call can be considered to occur in two main
88 contexts: predation (alarm or mobbing calls) and social (contact, separation, or
89 territorial calls) contexts (Marler 1956, 2004; Randler and Förschler 2011). Here, we
90 focus on studying the chink calls within the social context, but the predation context and
91 environmental effects on bird communication are also introduced below to propose a
92 potential trade-off that might influence the characteristics of these social calls.

93 Despite the evolutionary advantages conferred by vocalizations in their respective
94 functions, both songs and calls can also entail energetic costs and heighten detectability
95 by predators (Ward and Slater 2005; Catchpole and Slater 2008; Stoddard and Salazar
96 2011). Therefore, it is expected that birds emit vocalizations when advantages outweigh
97 costs. In such circumstances, birds can modulate their vocalizations based on the
98 presence of potential mates or competitors, as well as the presence of predators (Zuk
99 and Kolluru 1998; Catchpole and Slater 2008). For instance, Abbey-Lee et al. (2015)
100 found that Great Tits (*Parus major*) exposed to predation risk decreased singing.
101 Santema et al. (2019) also found that songbirds were less likely to sing at dawn and
102 delayed the timing of their dawn singing under predation risk. Therefore, a trade-off in
103 communication arises: birds are motivated to produce vocalizations to convey messages
104 to conspecific, but they might also exhibit reluctance to communicate in order to avoid
105 predation. In the specific case of the Chaffinch chink calls, this trade-off might be
106 manifested in the number of notes emitted. Under predation risk, Chaffinches aiming to
107 convey social messages to conspecific might preferentially emit a single chink rather
108 than repeated notes, thereby facilitating communication while minimizing the risk of
109 detection by predators.

110 In addition to the presence of conspecific or heterospecific individuals, sound produced
111 by birds might vary depending on environmental features such as habitat structure or
112 environmental noise (Slabbekoorn 2004). Noisy environments, such as those found in
113 cities, can prompt birds to modify their vocalizations. For instance, great tits living in
114 urban areas produce songs with higher minimum frequencies to mitigate masking by
115 traffic noise (Slabbekoorn and Ripmeester 2008). Birds might also employ strategies to
116 mitigate the loss of information in communication, including matching their
117 vocalizations to the acoustic properties of their habitats (Hansen 1979). For instance, the

118 advertisement calls of Satin Bowerbirds (*Ptilonorhynchus violaceus*) vary depending on
119 habitat type (Nicholls and Goldizen 2006). Dense foliage in forests increases sound
120 attenuation (Martens 1980; Blumenrath and Dabelsteen 2004), prompting birds to use
121 strategies such as singing from perches high up in the vegetation to enhance sound
122 transmission (Catchpole and Slater 2008; Barker et al. 2009). Pérez-González et al.
123 (2021) proposed that birds might utilize quartzitic scree slopes in Mediterranean forests
124 to favour sound transmission. Their hypothesis is based on the acoustic properties of
125 these open and rocky areas, characterized by high acoustic impedance and reflectivity
126 (Pérez-González et al. 2021).

127 In this study, we investigate whether habitat structure can influence the characteristics
128 of the social/chink call emitted by Chaffinches in a Mediterranean forest. The
129 Mediterranean forest of central-western Spain is extensively distributed in quartzite
130 mountainous areas, where large steep stones are abundant. These scree slopes, known as
131 *pedrizas* in Spanish, provide open habitats with high sound transmission capabilities
132 (Pérez-González et al. 2021). However, *pedrizas* can also facilitate the attack of raptors
133 such as the sparrowhawk (*Accipiter nisus*), goshawk (*A. gentilis*) or booted eagle
134 (*Hieraaetus pennatus*), which might enter the forest canopy through these open areas.
135 The conditions on and near *pedrizas* contrast with those within the forest, where sound
136 transmission decreases (Martens 1980; Catchpole and Slater 2008; Pérez-González et al.
137 2021), and the dense foliage hinders the efficacy of predation by raptors (Preston 1990).
138 Therefore, stimuli that trigger or prevent social calls in Chaffinches differ within the
139 forest and on/near *pedrizas*. Consequently, the features of chink calls emitted by
140 Chaffinches might differ in both type of areas in the Mediterranean forest. It could be
141 expected that Chaffinches tend to communicate with conspecific using single chink
142 calls in *pedrizas* due to the higher predation risk and sound transmission. Therefore,

143 here, we assess the hypothesis that the number of repeats of the chink calls produced by
144 Chaffinches is smaller near pedrizas than within the forest.

145

146 **Methods**

147 **Study Area and Data Collection**

148 The study was carried out in the Mediterranean forest of Monfragüe National Park,
149 situated in central-western Spain. This forest primarily comprises oak trees (*Quercus*
150 *suber*, *Q. ilex*, or *Q. faginea*) and several scrub species such as strawberry tree (*Arbutus*
151 *unedo*), false olive (*Phillyrea angustifolia*), or heaths (*Erica* spp.). Here, the
152 Mediterranean forest often intercalates with scree slopes of quartzite origin (pedrizas,
153 Fig. 1a), formed by gelifraction processes during the Quaternary period (Pulido-
154 Fernández et al. 2013).

155 A portable Zoom H6 recorder with Roland Binaural microphones was used to record
156 bird vocalizations. Binaural microphones (model CS-10EM) were placed in the ears of
157 the researcher, who faced north during the entire recording. These omnidirectional
158 microphones aided in distinguishing between vocalizations originating from different
159 locations and helped to avoid the conflation of calls from different individuals into a
160 same call. One researcher, holding the recorder in hand, recorded the soundscape at six
161 sampling points in a patch of the Mediterranean forest (Fig. 1b). Three sampling points
162 were located within the forest, while three points were situated at the southern edge of
163 respective pedrizas. The vegetation species composition was homogeneous in the
164 studied patch of forest, and only the scree slopes changed habitat features. The sizes of
165 the pedrizas are 3450.63 m² (western pedriza; point 2), 3342.04 m² (central pedriza;
166 point 3), and 5886.85 m² (eastern pedriza; point 5). The minimum distance between

167 pedrizas is over 100 m (between pedrizas 2 and 3). The recordings were consistently
168 collected by the same researcher (JAGF), who always wore the same type of clothes
169 with different combinations of brown and olive colours. During the recording, the
170 researcher stayed in the same point and avoided any movement.

171 Before recording, the researcher waited for 2 minutes while scanning for predators
172 around the sampling point. The recording commenced when the researcher inferred that
173 there were no predators (bird or mammal) in the vicinity. It is noteworthy that
174 Chaffinches may not perceive a human presence in their territory as a threat (Budka et
175 al. 2019); indeed, the bird community of the Monfragüe National Park exhibits high
176 levels of habituation to human presence (Pérez-González et al. 2024). The intensity and
177 frequency of the recorded chink calls were not indicative of mobbing calls (Randler and
178 Förschler 2011) emitted due to the presence of non-detected predators by the researcher.
179 Therefore, we assumed that all the recorded chink calls were produced under a social
180 context (contact/separation/territoriality).

181 Eight measurement campaigns were conducted during daylight hours. A measurement
182 campaign involved obtaining a 10-minute recording at each of the 6 sampling points of
183 the study area. We carried out two measurement campaigns in each season: summer
184 (3rd and 10th of July 2022), autumn (6th and 13th of November 2022), winter (12th and
185 19th of February 2023), and spring (26th of March and 2nd of April 2023). The
186 recordings were conducted consecutively and commenced at the same solar hour (one
187 hour after the sunrise) in all the measurement campaigns. Within each season, each
188 measurement campaign was conducted with different orientation: one campaign started
189 at point 1 and concluded at point 6 (orientation 1), and the other campaign began at
190 point 6 and concluded at point 1 (orientation 2).

191 **Data Analysis**

192 All the 48 recordings (6 sampling points x 8 measurement campaigns) were managed
193 and analysed using the free software Sonic Visualiser (www.sonicvisualiser.org/). In the
194 soundscape of the recordings, we identified the Chaffinch chink calls and noted whether
195 the call consisted of a single chink or a repetition of notes. In the cases of repetition of
196 notes, the number of repetitions was scored. Therefore, for each recording, we obtained
197 a list of numbers ranging from 1 to 4, representing the number of repeats observed in
198 the Chaffinch chink calls.

199 Weather conditions varied among seasons and might have influenced the detection of
200 Chaffinch calls (ISO 9113-1 1993). Most of weather-related variables were accounted
201 for in subsequent analyses by including season as a factor in the models (see below).
202 However, wind conditions fluctuated between days within the same season and even
203 between sampling points on the same day. Therefore, wind conditions were considered
204 in the analyses. Wind conditions were categorized into three levels: no wind (wind
205 speed less than 1 m/s), wind (wind speed between 1 and 5 m/s) and strong wind (wind
206 speed greater than 5 m/s). Wind speed was measured using an anemometer (Skywatch
207 Geos 11) during the recordings. Wind speeds exceeding 5 m/s can introduce significant
208 sound interference (ISO 1996-2 2017), so recordings under strong wind were excluded
209 from the analyses. Out of the 48 recordings, 6 were categorized under strong wind
210 conditions (3 points on pedrizas: point 5 on the 3rd of July, point 3 on the 10th of July,
211 and point 5 on the 12th of February; 3 points in forest: point 6 on the 3rd of July, point 6
212 on the 12th of February, and point 6 on the 19th of February). These were removed,
213 leaving a final dataset consisting of 420 minutes of recording (42 recordings x 10
214 minutes). These remaining recordings were categorized as either no wind or wind for
215 the subsequent analyses (see below).

216

217 **Statistical Analyses**

218 The number of call repeats of the chink calls recorded on pedrizas (points 2, 3, and 5)
219 was compared with those recorded in the forest (points 1, 4, and 6) using a Generalized
220 Linear Model (GLM) fitted by maximum likelihood with Poisson distribution. This
221 analysis was performed using the ‘glm’ function in R (R Core Team 2019). Initially this
222 model was conducted without any additional variable. However, we also conducted a
223 Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) with the number of repeats as the
224 explanatory variable and habitat feature (forest vs. pedriza), season (summer, autumn,
225 winter, and spring), wind (no wind vs. wind) and orientation (orientation 1 vs.
226 orientation 2) as fixed factors; sampling point was included as random effect. This
227 GLMM was performed using the ‘glmer’ function from the ‘lme4’ package (Bates et al.
228 2015) in R. We initially included all double interactions between fixed factors, but the
229 model was simplified by a backward stepwise procedure tending to minimize the
230 Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Multicollinearity in the obtained models was
231 checked using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) with the ‘vif’ function from the ‘car’
232 package (Fox and Weisberg 2019) in R. We considered multicollinearity to be
233 problematic when VIF scores exceeded 5.

234 The analyses were repeated by selecting the chink calls emitted by Chaffinches that
235 were situated near the recorder (close calls). See Fig. S1 and related information in the
236 Supplementary Material for the procedure used to select close calls. The close calls
237 were emitted by Chaffinches that were located near the recorder, but we were unable to
238 determine the exact distance of the birds (see Fig. S1 and related information in
239 Supplementary Material).

240

241 Results

242 During the 420-minute recording, a total of 2038 chink calls were recorded. The highest
243 number of calls per recording was obtained in autumn (mean \pm standard deviation (SD)
244 in autumn: 83.67 ± 67.76 ; spring: 47.67 ± 50.18 ; winter: 37.33 ± 47.49 ; summer: 14.00
245 ± 18.15). Among the recorded chink calls, 718 were single calls, 914 had two repeats,
246 355 had three repeats, and 51 had four repeats. The number of repeats was lower on
247 pedrizas than in forest (mean \pm SD = 1.72 ± 0.73 on pedrizas; mean \pm SD = 2.02 ± 0.80
248 in forest; GLM (forest as reference): $\beta = -0.17$, $SE(\beta) = 0.03$, $Z = -5.11$, $P < 0.001$; Fig.
249 2). This difference persisted across all seasons (Habitat feature * Season interaction was
250 removed from results in Table 1; see Fig. 3a) and orientations (Habitat feature *
251 Orientation was removed from results in Table 1; see Fig. 3b). The number of repeats in
252 the chink calls was higher when the recordings were conducted in winter (Table 1, Fig.
253 3a) and with orientation 2. The effect of orientation on the number of repeats varied
254 depending on the season (Table 1, Fig. S2 in Supplementary Material). The effect of
255 wind conditions was not significant (Table 1).

256 When we only considered the close calls (N = 391), the number of repeats in the chink
257 calls continued to be lower on the pedrizas than in the forest, and the difference was
258 even greater (mean \pm SD = 1.45 ± 0.54 on pedrizas; mean \pm SD = 2.18 ± 0.88 in forest;
259 GLM (forest as reference): $\beta = -0.41$, $SE(\beta) = 0.08$, $Z = -5.39$, $P < 0.001$; Fig. 4). This
260 difference persisted across all seasons (Habitat feature * Season interaction was
261 removed from results in Table 2) and orientations (Habitat feature * Orientation
262 interaction was removed from results in Table 2). As above, the effect of wind
263 conditions was not significant (Table 2).

264

265 **Discussion**

266 Our results support the hypothesis that the number of repeats of the Chaffinch chink
267 calls was smaller near pedrizas than in the surrounding forest. This result can be
268 considered as additional evidence of the impact of quartzite scree slopes (pedrizas) on
269 the communicative behaviour of birds (Pérez-González et al. 2021). Moreover, our
270 findings support the effect of habitat features on the characteristics of avian
271 communicative behaviour (e.g. Blumenrath and Dabelsteen 2004; Nicholls and
272 Goldizen 2006).

273 Previous studies have focused on Chaffinch chink calls, shedding light on both the
274 ultimate and proximate causes of this type of vocalization. For instance, Budka et al.
275 (2019) investigated the response of chink calls to playback and inferred their possible
276 function as alarm signals. Randler and Förschler (2011) studied the chink vocalization
277 in a predation context and suggested its function as a mobbing call. Riebel and Slater
278 (2019) provided evidence of the importance of learning in chink call development. Our
279 study contributes to the understanding of the proximate causes of Chaffinch chink calls
280 in the absence of predation risk. We found that, in a social context (Marler 1956, 2004),
281 the characteristics of chink calls in terms of number of repeated notes varied depending
282 on habitat features.

283 Our findings support the existence of a trade-off occurring in bird communication
284 (Morrell 2004; Abbey-Lee et al. 2015; Santema et al. 2019). Under certain conditions,
285 such as the presence of conspecifics or the absence of predators, motivations for social
286 call emissions might stimulate sound production (Catchpole and Slater 2008).
287 Contrarily, the presence of predators might inhibit the production of social calls
288 (Santema et al. 2019). There could be situations in which stimuli promoting social call
289 emissions coexist with stimuli inhibiting such behaviour, requiring birds to modulate

290 their communication by weighing the benefits against the costs (Abbey-Lee et al. 2015).
291 In our study system, the pedrizas are open areas where predation risk can increase
292 (Preston 1990), but they also possess acoustic properties that facilitate sound
293 transmission and might prompt birds to communicate (Pérez-González et al. 2021). The
294 coexistence of both types of stimuli (those triggering and those deterring social calls) in
295 the pedrizas might be in conflict and affect the characteristics of bird communicative
296 signals (Abbey-Lee et al. 2015, Santema et al. 2019). Chaffinches can respond by
297 producing social calls but reducing the duration of the vocalizations to prevent the
298 attention of undetected predators.

299 The use of the number of repeats as the study variable presents challenges. On one
300 hand, the number of repeated notes of the Chaffinch chink call can be important to
301 determine its function (Marler 1956; Randler and Förschler 2011). The number of
302 repeats increases significantly in the presence of predators, which motivate alarm and
303 mobbing calls (Marler 1956; Saur et al. 1996, Glutz von Blotzheim and Bauer 1997;
304 Randler and Förschler 2011). Although we did not observe any predator during the
305 recordings, we cannot completely rule out the possibility that some calls were motivated
306 by a predator that was not detected by the researcher. However, since 80% of the
307 recorded calls were single or composed by two notes, we might infer that the predation
308 risk had low effect on our results. Moreover, the main results remained consistent when
309 we analysed the close calls, for which the detection of a predator by the researcher was
310 easier. In addition to the potential effect of undetected predators, varying individual
311 densities around the sampling points might also influence the intensity of social
312 interactions and the number of call repeats (Ripmeester et al. 2010). Despite the habitat
313 was homogenous throughout the studied path of forest (aside from the presence or
314 absence of pedrizas), we were unable to infer individual densities in the vicinity of the

315 sampling points, and this variable might have impacted our data collection. On the other
316 hand, repeated chink calls might be considered when two or more birds produce single
317 calls sequentially with the same time span as a repeated chink call. Despite the use of
318 binaural microphones reducing the effect of this situation, we cannot rule out the
319 overestimation of the number of repeats in calls from more than one Chaffinch with
320 similar spatial locations. The high proportion of single calls and the general low number
321 of repeats in our dataset suggest a weak effect of this situation. Finally, wind conditions
322 prevented the use of 6 recordings in our analyses, and this factor varied among the
323 recordings that were analysed. While we did not find significant effects of wind
324 conditions in our results, designing strategies to mitigate the impact of wind on
325 recordings could enhance the quality of data collection in future studies (Priyadarshani
326 et al. 2018). All these factors can affect the reliability of data collection, but their
327 influences are likely to be similar both within the forest and near pedrizas, allowing the
328 main conclusion of this study to remain valid.

329 We repeated the comparison of the number of calls repeats based on habitat features
330 using close calls. The difference of call repeats recorded near pedrizas and in the forest
331 was higher for close calls, which supports the conclusion that the number of call repeats
332 emitted by Chaffinches near pedrizas is lower. However, the categorization of
333 Chaffinch calls as close calls, as described in Supplementary Material (Fig. S1), can be
334 influenced by factors such as the orientation of the bird relative to the microphone, wind
335 conditions, foliage density (Martens 1980; Blumenrath and Dabelsteen 2004), volume
336 of the playback, microphone sensitivity, or the gain settings and properties of the audio
337 recorder (Zollinger et al. 2012). Consequently, we were unable to estimate the exact
338 distance between the birds emitting calls and the recorder. Although the distance to the
339 recorder could vary for each Chaffinch with calls categorized as close calls, the

340 procedure described in the Supplementary Material allowed us to select a subset of calls
341 (391 out of 2038) that were emitted near the recorder.

342 The effect of the presence of pedrizas on the number of repeats of chink calls persisted
343 across all seasons and orientations. However, the differences between seasons and
344 between orientations suggest additional elements that might influence bird
345 communication (Hanski and Laurila 1993, Rose et al. 2021). In our entire dataset, the
346 number of repeats in the chink calls was higher during the winter. This increase might
347 be due to a change in the possible function of the social call, which might be mostly
348 emitted with a territorial function prior to the mating season rather than for contact
349 purposes. During the spring, the territorial communications might be focused on songs
350 (Marler 2004), and territorial calls might lose importance. In our recordings, 98% of the
351 songs were recorded in spring, with the remaining songs in winter (Pérez-González,
352 unpublished data). Furthermore, the influence of weather conditions on bird
353 communication (Cordonnier et al. 2023) might also affect our results. For instance,
354 temperature and humidity influence attenuation due to atmospheric absorption (ISO
355 9313-1 1993). In the context discussed in this work, sound attenuation might prompt
356 Chaffinches to produce higher number of repeats in their social calls to enhance
357 communication. The lower temperatures and the mean humidity of around 60% during
358 winter (Guillén et al. 2018) might result in the highest attenuation for the predominant
359 frequencies of the chink calls (see Fig. S1 in Supplementary Material). Future studies
360 could focus on the impact of weather conditions on the repetitiveness of Chaffinch calls
361 by designing measurement campaigns that maintain low variation in habitat features
362 while varying weather conditions such as temperature and humidity.

363 The number of repeats also varied depending on the spatial orientation for the collection
364 of recordings. In general, the number of repeats was higher when the researcher used

365 orientation 2 (from point 6 to point 1). However, this result varied depending on the
366 season (Fig. S2 in Supplementary Material). We do not have a clear explanation for
367 these differences, as several processes might influence the communication system. On
368 one hand, the intensity of bird communication can differ throughout the day (Bruni et
369 al. 2014; Pérez-Granados et al. 2018), so the communicative context might be different
370 at the firsts and lasts points within the same measurement campaign. Furthermore, the
371 recorded data depend on the distribution of the territorial edges, a factor that we did not
372 assess. These phenomena can vary throughout the seasons (Nice 1941; Quispe et al.
373 2017). Additionally, the function and motivation of the calls can change throughout the
374 year (Marler 2004). The combined action of all these phenomena might be responsible
375 for the higher number of chink repeats in orientation 2 and for the effect on the Season *
376 Orientation interaction on the number of repeats.

377 The effect of habitat features on bird songs is well studied (Slabbekoorn and Smith
378 2002; Nicholls and Goldizen 2006; Derryberry 2009). For instance, the acoustic
379 adaptation hypothesis, which proposes certain acoustic characteristics for bird
380 vocalizations produced in densely vegetated habitats, is mainly applied to songs
381 (Boncoraglio and Saino 2007). On the other hand, variations of calls characteristics
382 depending on the social environment or the presence of heterospecific have been
383 proposed in several studies (Carlson et al. 2020; Jablonszky et al. 2021). However, the
384 possibility of variations of calls characteristics depending on habitat features has been
385 poorly studied, and our work can be considered a contribution to the role of calls in bird
386 communication, an issue that is needed of further research (Marler 2004).

387

388 **Statements and declarations**

389 **Competing interests:** The authors have no competing interests to declare that are
390 relevant to the content of this article.

391 **Ethics approval:** We did not need any licences, permits or ethical approval for the
392 study. No animals were captured nor manipulated during the study. We did not alter the
393 habitat during the collection of recordings. The sampling points were in public ways
394 that can be used by tourist. The researcher with the recorder tried not to disturb the
395 fauna.

396 **Author Contributions:** Conceptualization: J.P-G., S.J.H.T, and G.R.G.; Data curation:
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403

404 **References**

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546 **Figure Captions**

547

548 **Fig.1.** Image of a quartzite scree slope (pedriza; a) and spatial location of the sampling
549 points and pedrizas in a patch of Mediterranean forest in the Monfragüe National Park
550 (b).

551

552 **Fig. 2.** Kernel density of Chaffinch chink calls depending on the number of repeats.
553 Grey line: chink calls recorded within the forest (N = 1068). Black line: chink calls
554 recorded on pedrizas (N = 970).

555

556

557 **Fig. 3.** Number of repeats in the Chaffinch chink calls depending on habitat (forest vs.
 558 pedrizas) under different conditions: a) Different seasons. b) Different orientation (see
 559 text for details). Figure shows means and standard errors, as well as the sample sizes
 560 (N) per season/orientation and habitat feature.

561

562 **Fig. 4.** Kernel density of Chaffinch close calls depending on the number of repeats.

563 Grey line: chink calls recorded within the forest (N = 179). Black line: chink calls

564 recorded on pedrizas (N = 212).

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573 **Table 1.** Effect of habitat feature (forest vs. pedrizas) on the number of chink call
574 repeats in Chaffinch. Results from a GLMM with number of call repeats as dependent
575 variable, habitat feature (sampling point within forest vs. sampling point on pedrizas),
576 season, wind conditions (no wind vs. wind) and orientation (orientation 1 vs. orientation
577 2) as fixed factors; sampling point was included as random effect. Forest as reference
578 for habitat feature. Winter as reference for Season variable. Wind as reference for wind
579 conditions. Orientation 2 as reference for Orientation variable. SE: standard error. SD:
580 standard deviation. AIC: 5639.9; VIF scores: 1.028 (Habitat feature), 1.586 (Season),
581 2.478 (wind), 4.518 (Orientation), 2.219 (Season*Orientation).

582

Term	Estimate	SE	Variance	SD	Z	P
Fixed factors						
Intercept	0.871	0.054			16.149	<0.001
Habitat feature (forest vs. pedriza)	-0.152	0.053			-2.853	0.004
Season (winter vs. autumn)	-0.299	0.105			-2.844	0.005
Season (winter vs. spring)	-0.178	0.108			-1.639	0.101
Season (winter vs. summer)	-0.122	0.125			-0.976	0.329
Wind conditions (no wind vs. wind)	0.052	0.092			0.569	0.569
Orientation (Or. 2 vs. Or. 1)	-0.734	0.163			-4.490	<0.001
Season (autumn) * Orientation (Or. 1)	0.667	0.171			3.900	<0.001
Season (spring) * Orientation (Or. 1)	0.814	0.189			4.307	<0.001
Season (summer) * Orientation (Or. 1)	0.475	0.229			2.075	0.038
Random effect						
Sampling point			0.002	0.046		

583

584 **Table 2.** Effect of habitat feature (forest vs. pedrizas) on the number of repeats in close
585 calls of Chaffinch. Results from a GLMM with number of call repeats as dependent
586 variable, habitat feature (sampling point within forest vs. sampling point on pedrizas),
587 season, wind conditions (no wind vs. wind) and orientation (orientation 1 vs. orientation
588 2) as fixed factors; sampling point was included as random effect. Forest as reference
589 for habitat feature. Winter as reference for Season variable. Wind as reference for wind
590 conditions. Orientation 2 as reference for Orientation variable. SE: standard error. SD:
591 standard deviation. AIC: 1057.9; VIF scores: 1.035 (Habitat feature), 1.116 (Season),
592 1.478 (wind), 1.162 (Orientation).

593

Term	Estimate	SE	Variance	SD	Z	P
Fixed factors						
Intercept	0.318	0.193			1.645	0.100
Habitat feature (forest vs. pedriza)	-0.303	0.114			-2.648	0.008
Season (winter vs. autumn)	0.510	0.225			2.265	0.023
Season (winter vs. spring)	0.575	0.203			2.837	0.005
Season (winter vs. summer)	0.799	0.336			2.378	0.017
Wind conditions (no wind vs. wind)	-0.124	0.137			-0.903	0.367
Orientation (Or. 2 vs. Or. 1)	-0.013	0.092			-0.147	0.882
Random effect						
Sampling point			0.007	0.081		

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